

4. Regenerated plantlets showing rooting on MS medium containing 1.0 mg IBA L⁻¹.

containing 1.0 mg IBA L⁻¹ (Fig. 4) and were transferred to pots.

Results indicated the usefulness of L-tryptophan and activated charcoal in increasing regeneration of green plants from long-term callus cultures of indica rice. ■

Grain quality

Modeling water uptake and degree of polish of milled rice

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This study was undertaken to model the process of water uptake behavior during cooking and to correlate water uptake with degree of polish for two varieties (coarse Jaya and scented fine Basmati) commonly grown in the western part of Uttar Pradesh, India. Rough rice samples were collected from a farmer's field just after harvest, cleaned, and shade-dried up to milling moisture content (14% dry basis). These were then shelled and polished in a

Satake rice sheller and polisher. Milling / polish time varied from 0 s to 60 s to control the degree of bran removal (degree of polish) with an increment of 15 s. The degree of polish of milled samples ranged from 2.7% to 8.4% for Jaya and 2.9% to 8.5% for Basmati at 15 s and 60 s, respectively.

The 1,000-kernel weight of Jaya (28.6 g) was higher than that of Basmati (24.5 g). The length and width-thickness ratio of Jaya were 8.67 mm and 3.04 mm, respectively, and those of Basmati were 11.09 mm and 5.13 mm. The angle of repose of Basmati (32°) was wider than Jaya's (24.8°). Bulk and true density were determined by measuring the weight of known volumes of samples and by the method of relative density, respectively. Porosity, the index of void space in the bulk, was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Porosity} = \frac{(\text{True density} - \text{bulk density})}{\text{True density}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Table 1 shows the bulk density, true density, and porosity of the two rice varieties.

Table 1. Physical and gravimetric properties of Jaya and Basmati rice.

Property	Jaya	Basmati
Size (mm)		
Length	8.7	11.1
Width	2.8	2.0
Thickness	2.0	1.8
1,000-kernel weight (g)	28.6	24.5
Bulk density (g cc ⁻¹)	0.6	0.5
True density (g cc ⁻¹)	1.3	1.0
Porosity (%)	51.2	51.4
Angle of repose(°)	24.8	32.6

Table 2. Degree of polish, head yield, and water uptake of Jaya and Basmati rice varieties.

Time of milling (s)	Jaya			Basmati		
	D _p ^a	H _y	W _{up}	D _p	H _y	W _{up}
0	0	89.0	-	0	85.0	-
15	2.7	64.3	355	2.9	65.1	352
30	4.6	61.9	357	4.9	63.9	362
45	6.7	58.1	362	6.4	63.1	371
60	8.4	57.2	368	8.5	63.0	384

^aD_p = degree of polish (% on brown rice basis), H_y = head yield (%), and W_{up} = water uptake (g).

Water uptake and kernel elongation after cooking were also determined (Table 2). Kernel elongation was 35% more in Basmati than in Jaya for 6% degree of polish. A similar observation was recorded for different samples of milled rice. Water uptake was found to be more for the same degree of polish for Basmati than for Jaya. Water uptake behavior for Jaya and Basmati can be described by the following equation:

$$W_{\text{up}} = A \times e^{B D_p} \quad (2)$$

where A = 1.71 and B = 0.91.

This mathematical expression describes the kinetics of water uptake (mL) and its relation with degree of polish (%) satisfactorily under obtainable conditions. The correlation coefficient and standard error of estimate for the above equation were 0.987 and 0.089, respectively. ■

Breeding of Gan wan nuo 5, a new high-quality glutinous indica variety

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Gan wan nuo 5, released in 1993 by the Jiangxi Provincial Seed Board, is a new glutinous indica rice variety with high quality. It was derived from the cross MY82166/Ma ba xian nuo. MY82166 is an indica rice with high resistance to blast, whereas Ma ba xian nuo is an aromatic glutinous indica variety. Gan wan nuo 5 is suitable for later season planting in the double-cropped area of southern China and single-cropped area of central China. Yield of this variety averaged 6.8 t ha⁻¹ in double-cropped areas; it was 7.5 t ha⁻¹ in single-cropped areas. This yield was 7% more than that of Jing Nuo 6, a glutinous check, and nearly the same as that of Shan you 63, a check hybrid. Because of its high quality and other good traits (see table), the award-winning Gan wan nuo 5 is replacing Jing Nuo 6 in many areas.